

Short observations on the judiciary system in occupied Western Sahara

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(Image diffused by Moroccan media during Gdeim Izik trial in 2017)

Introduction

As International Observer and member of Fundación Sahara Occidental and collaborator of porunsaharalibre.org, I have been attending trials of Saharawi Political Prisoners, both in the occupied territories of Western Sahara as well as in Morocco, and also monitoring the situation on the ground in respect to human rights related issues for almost a decade.

Although I have been publishing reports since 2013 on these issues, the questions put forward by many readers and also during conferences and interviews let me believe that it is necessary to write a brief information on the proceedings since the arrest/abduction in the occupied territories until the conviction of Saharawi political prisoners.

In my report The Gdeim Izik Case¹, several testimonies are illustrative of the way Saharawi are “arrested”/abducted and what follows until the final accusation. Although it is the most high-profile case, other cases are similar in regards to the proceedings of the Moroccan police and judiciary system.

¹ <https://es.scribd.com/document/366418567/The-Gdeim-Izik-Case>

A typical case

The over 100 testimonies that I have recollected over the years are very similar, being the main difference, the intensity of violence suffered by the person that is arrested/abducted i.e. the torture endured.

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It starts always with an arrest or abduction where no arrest or search warrant is shown, usually violence is applied since the first moment by the agents that can be in uniform, part of the special commando forces (and in that case wearing masks), or in civil clothes. The agents are from the Moroccan police force, the gendarmerie or the intelligence service.

The “accused” can be taken in midst of a public street, in his family house, during a social event or a demonstration. This “arrest” is made with public violence which can in some cases even exercised upon the family members or friends present.

He is thrown inside a vehicle and then taken either to an unknown location or directly to police or gendarmerie headquarters.

If brought to an unknown location torture² will be applied, both physical as psychological, in the police or gendarmerie headquarters the same faith awaits the “detained” during an interrogation period that can take several hours to several days, depending on how long it takes for the detained to sign the documents written by the Moroccan authorities. Neither lawyers nor families are informed about the whereabouts of the detained in due time.

In several interviews the ex-political prisoners told me that they are presented with “special files”, which means that their cases are special cases with a different colored file folder, with orders directly from Rabat for the authorities in Western Sahara.

If arrested in Western Sahara the first appearance in front of a judge is in most cases made without the presence of a lawyer, in all testimonies I have taken the same is said: “ I denounced the torture I have been subjected to but the judge did not want to hear about it”, in some cases judges even say some “funny remark” or insult the detained. Although many of the detainees are presented to the judge with obvious wounds and even bloody no investigation is ordered by the judge. The request of investigation into torture is denied systematically.

The ordeal of the detainees continues until the final judgement in the appeal trial.

² <https://porunsaharalibre.org/informes/report-saharawi-political-prisoners-november-2016/>

The trials do not respect the minimum criteria of fairness, the presumption of innocence is never taken in account during the proceedings, the defense lawyers are harassed, not allowed to present exculpatory evidence, defense witnesses are not summoned nor admitted by the judges. The “accused” are insulted by the judges, humiliated and always treated as they were already convicted criminals. All the cases are based solely on documents signed under extreme coercion or torture and “evidences” that are produced and have no identification to where, when or by whom they were found nor is there any chain of custody.

References to their political beliefs and the “reaffirmation” that Western Sahara is “Moroccan Sahara” are made not only by the prosecutor but also by the judge himself.

Judges often “double” their competence, making themselves “expertise evaluations” in the medical field or as “graphologists” and throughout the trials give their personal opinion mimicking the state’s political views on the Western Sahara issue.

Independence of the Judiciary

Without going into in a in-depth analysis it is obvious that there is no independence of the judiciary in Western Sahara or in Morocco concerning the Saharawi population.

Although the independence of the Judiciary is enshrined in the Moroccan constitution and law, and in theory guaranteed by the state, Article 107 of the Moroccan constitution states that:

“The judicial power is independent of the legislative power and of the executive power.

The King is the guarantor of the independence of the judicial power. “

The “sovereignty and unity” of the Kingdom is one of the most, if not, the most, important base of Morocco, in view of course of the occupation of Western Sahara, and a taboo theme. To exhibit a flag of Western Sahara or even say Western Sahara instead of the terminology imposed by the State : “Moroccan Sahara” or “Provinces of the South” is considered an attempt against the integrity of the Kingdom.

So, we have the judiciary system of the occupying power **“independent” from the Government but never from the maximum authority which is the King of Morocco** and who’s main goal is to maintain the non-autonomous territory of Western Sahara under occupation resorting to a regime of total control of the population, which is clear by the amount of Moroccan armed forces, police and gendarmerie, the forced change of demographics with the introduction of hundreds of thousands of settlers and the military separation wall, heavily armed with 2720km and the most mined area per capita in the world, transforming the occupied area in prison with controlled land, air and sea borders, and a Saharawi population under siege.

This by itself is clear evidence that there can be no independence of the judiciary system concerning the Saharawi population.

The judiciary therefore is not able to decide on matters concerning the Saharawi Population brought before them impartially, on the basis of facts or in accordance with the law. The Saharawi are seen

“as guilty for existing” as stated by the judges and prosecutors who say that there is no such thing as Western Sahara and that all are Moroccan citizens, since the Saharawi born before the occupation where stripped from their Spanish nationality and all born after the occupation forced to have Moroccan nationality. The judiciary has from the starting point restrictions, improper influences, inducements, pressures, threats and interferences, from the Kingdom.

Ignacio Cembrero a Spanish journalist published a confidential report by Robert Jackson, political attaché of the US Embassy in Rabat, dated August 24, 2009 on the Moroccan justice under the theme "justice through telephone calls interceding in the operation of the courts "that questions judicial independence³ in it we can read.

3. (C) *When PolOff asked prominent judicial reform activist Abdelaziz Nouyidi to comment on the degree of judicial independence in Morocco, he laughed. "When it deals with anything political, there is zero independence. When it has to do with the press, there is zero independence. With all other cases, there is more room for independence, but not very much," he told PolOff. Nouyidi described an encounter with a judge who received a phone call from the Ministry of the Interior during their conversation. The judge, responding to the caller's questions, stated, "The verdict was what you wanted." Nouyidi said the judge immediately became embarrassed by having this conversation in front of an activist for judicial reform, but had been so accustomed to reporting on his cases to ministry officials that he had forgotten to be discreet.*

4. (C) *XXXXXXXXXXXXXX said the lack of independence allows the court system to be manipulated into an instrument of political repression. "Other countries use the army or the police to control politics," he mused, "but in Morocco, we use the justice system."*

Although the article is not recent the *modus operandis* continues the same, as was seen during the Gdeim Izik trial in 2016/2017, where all changes of strategy or unexpected occurrences during the trial were followed by “technical incidents” which lead to “interruptions” of the sessions and pauses that gave the judges time to exit the court room before taking decisions”.

Also, the amount of publicity and public “conviction” on TV’s and other state-owned media during the trial are a clear indicator of the lack of independence. In the Gdeim Izik case during one of the sessions, one of the accused was told to seat in a chair which had the word “terrorist” written on it (according to the judge from a previous trial) and this image was broadcasted. The fact that any person during an ongoing trial is forced to sit on a chair with the identification as “terrorist” indicates the lack of existence of “presumption of innocence” and the that no evidences are needed to convict.

³ http://www.elpais.com/articulo/internacional/Cable/funcionamiento/Justicia/Marruecos/elpepuint/20101220elpepuint_13/Tes

That a presiding judge allows this kind of event to take place in his court room is even more revealing.

I refer once again to my report on the Gdeim Izik case which was without doubt a trial that is evidence of the proceedings and lack of independence on all levels and was presented by the Moroccan authorities as a “fair and just trial in accordance with national and international law” as pointed out by the presiding judge each day of the trial in the courtroom and by the Moroccan media and government in public statements.

Facts are not taken in account by the judges when convicting Saharawi political prisoners, facts are not even accepted as admissible and the accusations are always vague without evidence of any harm doing.

Another problem is the obvious lack of knowledge of the Saharawi culture, society and language by the Moroccan judges, the fact that translators are not always available and the lack of understanding of a very different culture gives way to misinterpretations and wrong conclusions, also here we have several examples during the Gdeim Izik Trial.

The refusal in all phases of investigation of an impartial forensic expertise concerning the torture the detained are subjected too is another transversal fact in all trials. In the Gdeim Izik Trial the judges ordered a forensic expertise after 7 years of continuous demands by the political prisoners, but even this expertise did not in any way fulfill the requirements of the Istanbul protocol, was made by state employees and had several grave errors, like “copy pasting” of medical findings from the file of one prisoner to the other forgetting to change the name. The French defense lawyers report⁴ has a in-depth analysis of these forensic expertise.

The rights of the defense are not respected in trial, as was the case of the Gdeim Izik Trial, where the defense lawyers were constantly interrupted, the questions put forward to witnesses considered by the judges “as already answered” or “not relevant”, and even ended with the expulsion of defense lawyer Maître Olfa OULED (defense lawyer of all accused) and of Maître Ingrid METTON (defense lawyer of Naama Asfari) from the court room by force and in case of Maitre Ouled being physically harmed on the court premises.

Even after the trials the violation of the rights of the political prisoners continue as well as the torture. The complaints presented by the families themselves, the prisoners and their lawyers are ignored by the prosecutors, the ministry of justice, the ministry of human rights

⁴ <https://www.scribd.com/document/361222146/Rapport-d-observations-de-la-defense-sur-le-proces-de-Gdeim-Izik-devant-la-Cour-d-appel-de-Rabat-15-06-2017>

Conclusion

There is no doubt that Western Sahara is a non-autonomous territory under Moroccan occupation (as stated by the UN resolutions, the International Court, the Justice Court of the European Union and the African Union), international humanitarian law should be respected in the territory and although Morocco is the administrative power it cannot abduct Sahrawi Political Prisoners or civilians to another country, which represent a violation of the 4th Geneva Convention.

The Moroccan judiciary is not independent when it handles Saharawi cases, the “interest of national unity” prevails over law.

The proceedings are tainted by political opinions and positions of the Kingdom, never allowing the chance of a fair trial for Saharawi.

The violations of human rights, Moroccan and international law occur during the moment of the arrest until the final verdict and extend afterwards during the whole period of detention.

International mechanisms are ratified by Morocco but not respected nor applied in the case of Saharawi, serving the sole purpose of justifying international funding, and giving a “new face” to the regime.

The appeals, decisions, interim measures and advices issued by the UN mechanisms are ignored by the Moroccan government and the judges, in spite of having ratified and adhered to the Convention Against Torture and the Optional Protocol of Convention Against Torture.

Saharawi Political Prisoners who resort to the UN mechanisms are victims of reprisals as well as their families.

The complaints presented on a legal level by the lawyers during the detention period of their clients are continuously ignored and are not answered.

Therefore, we can conclude that Moroccan judiciary system has no independence on any level regarding the Saharawi Political Prisoners and that any improvements made are never applied to the Saharawi population.

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